

Gender-Responsive Governance, Social Service Delivery, and Community Satisfaction in SAMARICA Area

Francis Mae G. Felipe-Mangupit

Occidental Mindoro State College

amaezzing131@gmail.com

Article Details:

Received: 17 January 2026

Revised: 10 April 2026

Accepted: 22 April 2026

Published: 11 May 2026

Corresponding Email:

amaezzing131@gmail.com

Recommended Citation:

Mangupit, F. M. G. (2026). Gender-Responsive Governance, Social Service Delivery, and Community Satisfaction in SAMARICA Area. *The International Review of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1 (5), 320-331.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20125910>

Index Terms:

gender-responsive governance, social service delivery, community satisfaction

Abstract. This study examined the extent of gender-responsive governance (GRG) implementation and its relationship to the quality of social service delivery and the level of community satisfaction in the SAMARICA area of Occidental Mindoro, Philippines. Employing descriptive-correlational and predictive research designs, the study assessed key dimensions of GRG, namely institutional mechanisms, protection and promotion of women's human rights, integration of the Gender and Development (GAD) agenda in local development plans, and resource allocation and financial accountability. It likewise evaluated the quality of social service delivery in terms of social welfare, health, safety and protection, and education-related services, and measured community satisfaction with GRG initiatives. The respondents included 385 community residents selected through proportional random sampling and 299 local government unit (LGU) officials and personnel involved in GAD-related programs. Data were gathered using the Gender-Responsive LGU (GeRL) Self-Assessment Tool developed by the Philippine Commission on Women and analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation, and multiple regression analysis at a 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that gender-responsive governance in the SAMARICA area is strongly implemented, particularly in protecting women's rights, integrating the GAD agenda in local plans, and establishing institutional mechanisms. Social service delivery was generally rated very good, with education, welfare, and health services receiving high evaluations. Results further showed that while GRG significantly influences the quality of social service delivery, it does not necessarily translate into higher community satisfaction. Among GRG indicators, policies protecting and promoting women's human rights emerged as the strongest predictor of community satisfaction. Similarly, among social service indicators, only safety and protection services significantly predicted community satisfaction. These findings underscore the importance of rights-based and protection-oriented interventions in enhancing public satisfaction with gender-responsive governance.

Introduction

Gender equality and inclusive governance are widely recognized as essential to sustainable development and social justice, with strong implications for public service outcomes and community well-being (Audette et al., 2018). In governance studies, increasing attention has been given to how gender-responsive policies contribute not only to equity but also to overall societal satisfaction.

Previous research consistently shows that gender equality in governance is associated with improved life satisfaction and better service delivery outcomes. Cross-national studies have found that promoting gender equality benefits both women and men by enhancing overall well-being. Similarly, research in different national contexts highlights that government

responsiveness and effective public service delivery significantly influence community satisfaction, with inclusive and gender-sensitive policies further strengthening these effects.

Across these studies, there is a general agreement that gender-responsive governance enhances both institutional performance and citizen well-being. Literature provides limitations that are utilized not only in international but also in the lack of localized and particular context analyses. Most of the studies that focus on internal, national, or international data, reveals that gender-responsive governance is implemented, however, attention is very limited to this area; not only being experienced at the local level, but also, in geographically isolated and socioeconomically challenged sectors. In the Philippines setup, it is undeniably evident that the gap is existing across the regions of the country, where Gender and Development (GAD) frameworks were noticed by the law makers and promulgated policies such as the Magna Carta of Women (RA, 9710). While the local government units, being granted to incorporate gender issues and perspectives into the budget creation, planning, and delivery of service, still, there are narrow proofs on how to enforce these policies that allows the improvements be visible in social services and community satisfaction up to its utmost level.

It is important that these gaps to be addressed not only theoretically, but might as well practically. Without a thorough understanding about gender-responsive governance works in local governance settings would weaken the policy implementation, that may lead in to more people being deprived to get the topmost service delivery systems, and the trust to the public authorities may be challenged in terms of producing meaningful and evident outcomes for the communities. This is truly applicable in the SAMARICA area of Occidental Mindoro, where the people have to lean on to their local government services and where inclusive governance provides a very important role in focusing on the issues about vulnerability and inequality.

To help explain gender-responsive governance, special service delivery, and community satisfaction is anchored in important theories, in particular the New Public Service (NPS) framework by Denhart and Denhart (2015) and Gender and Development (GAD) Theory. These theories provide a strong foundation for look into how gender perspectives are integrated into local governance. While from a GAD Theory perspective which puts forth the value of gender-responsive approaches we have the NPS framework which brings to fore the issues of participation, accountability and public interest in the pursuit of more inclusive and which are responsive governance models.

In the face of which we still see gender inequality, service access issues, and local governance capacity problems it is important to look at what present gender responsive governance initiatives are doing for improved service delivery and citizen satisfaction. This study assessed the extent of gender-responsive governance implementation and its relationship to the quality of social service delivery and the level of community satisfaction in the SAMARICA area in Occidental Mindoro.

Specifically, this study aimed to determine the extent of gender-responsive governance implementation in SAMARICA area; asses the quality of social service delivery; measure the level of community satisfaction with gender-responsive governance; assess if there is a significant relationship between the extent of gender-responsive governance implementation and the quality of social service delivery; ascertain if there is a significant relationship between the extent of gender-responsive governance implementation and the level of community satisfaction; find out if there is a significant relationship between the quality of social service delivery and the level of community satisfaction; analyze which among the indicators of gender-responsive governance best predict the community satisfaction; and test which among the indicators of social service delivery best predict the community satisfaction in SAMARICA area.

Methodology

Study Design

This study utilized descriptive-correlational and predictive research design. The descriptive component aimed to assess the extent of implementation of gender-responsive governance in the SAMARICA area, focusing on key dimensions such as institutional mechanisms, policies on women's rights, integration of the GAD agenda in local development plans, and resource allocation and financial accountability. It also assessed the current state of social service delivery on welfare, health, protection, and education-related services, as well as gauged the level of community satisfaction across the implementation of gender-responsive governance. The correlation component determines the relationships between the implementation of gender-responsive governance and both the quality of social service delivery and the level of community satisfaction. In the end, the predictive component identified which aspects of gender-responsive governance and social service delivery served as predictors of community satisfaction.

Study Setting

This study was conducted in the SAMARICA area of Occidental Mindoro, Philippines. These municipalities were located in the southern part of the province and common geographical, economical, and cultural similarities, while also facing distinct governance and development situation.

San Jose serves as the commercial and administrative center of Occidental Mindoro and is the most urbanized among the four municipalities. It functions as a key hub for trade, transportation, and public services, and is home to several regional and provincial government offices.

Magsaysay is a rural municipality known for its agricultural lands and fishing communities. The local government plays an important role in delivering social services to a widely distributed population like living in coastal and upland barangays. Rizal is an interior municipality with a diverse agricultural base and a growing Indigenous Population (IP) which they serve through programs that include all and in particular which are left out.

In Calintaan you will find lowland and upland communities. It is located by mountains and also has forest reserves. The population is mostly Indigenous as in Rizal and also the local and national government agencies are involved. The SAMARICA area is a study in diversity of social, economic and cultural characteristics and does well in gender responsive governance. The mix of urban and rural elements gives a better look at how different communities use local policies, provide services, and implement gender-based programs.

Unit of Analysis and Sampling

The study involved individual residents of the SAMARICA region. The participants included both males and females from various sectors within the region. The population of this community was recorded as 170,983 in the year 2020. Using proportional random sampling, 385 individuals from the total number of residents in the region were selected for the study. Additionally, 299 officials of the local government districts (LGUs) were also selected for the study. These officials were selected from the total number of employees of LGUs, which numbered 1,179. The officials included in the LGU sample included the GAD focal points, social workers, health officers, barangay officials, and other staff members of the LGUs who are responsible for the Gender and Development programs in their districts. Each of the municipalities in the study – San Jose, Magsaysay, Rizal and Calintaan were included as separate groups within the study to ensure that the individuals within each of these groups was proportionally represented within the samples of both the residents and LGU officials. These sample sizes were calculated using Slovin's Formula.

Research Instrument

The research was undertaken using the Gender-Responsive LGU (GeRL) Self-Assessment Tool developed by the Philippine Commission on Women (PCW, 2018). This instrument was designed to assess LGU commitment to GAD, gender-responsive planning and budgeting, and the implementation of gender equality programs.

The instrument was composed of three main parts, each intended to assess different aspects of the implementation and impact of gender-responsive governance within the Local Government Unit (LGU).

Part I: Extent of the Implementation of Gender-Responsive Governance. In this Section determined the extent to which the policies and programs related to gender-responsive governance were actually implemented within the Local Government Unit (LGU). Each of these policies and programs were rated on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 – Not Implemented to 5 – Fully Implemented.

Part II: Quality of Social Service Delivery. In this section of the questionnaire assessed the availability and functionality of social services related to gender-responsive governance as provided by the LGU. Each of these services was rated on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 – Not Available to 5 – Highly Available.

Part III: Community Satisfaction with Gender-Responsive Governance. In this section of the survey aimed to determine the level of satisfaction that the community members had with the gender-responsive services that were provided to them by the LGU. Each respondent was to rate their level of satisfaction on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 – Very Dissatisfied to 5 – Very Satisfied.

Data Collection Procedure

The data for this investigation was collected with care and precision. In order to administer this survey to the women of these municipalities, the mayors of each of these municipalities was contacted and requested to permit the performance of this survey within their municipality.

Data Processing and Analysis

Descriptive and inferential statistical methods were used to analyze the data collected from the structured survey questionnaires. To provide an outline as regards to the level of gender-responsive governance implementation, the quality of social service delivery, and the weight of community satisfaction in the SAMARICA area, under the descriptive statistics, the mean and standard deviation were used. On the other hand, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to identify the strength of the impact and direction of the relationship between gender-responsive governance, social service delivery, and community satisfaction. Multiple Regression Analysis was also applied in order to diagnose the particular aspects of gender-responsive governance and social service delivery in consideration to its influence to the community satisfaction.

Software such as SPSS were utilized to every statistical analyses to make sure that the results will be accurate and reliable. To test all the hypotheses, 0.05 was used as the significance level.

Scope and Limitations

This study focused on evaluating the implementation of gender-responsive governance and its relationship with social service delivery and community satisfaction in the SAMARICA area, which comprised the municipalities of San Jose, Magsaysay, Rizal, and Calintaan in Occidental Mindoro, Philippines.

The study was limited to the SAMARICA area and did not include other municipalities in Occidental Mindoro. Thus, the findings may not have been generalizable to the entire province or other regions. Only adult residents were surveyed; children, out-of-school youth, and transient individuals were not included in the data collection. The study did not include a discussion of national level gender policies as it focused solely upon the local level of implementation of gender policies within the region studied.

Ethical Considerations

All of the participants in the study were made aware of the aims of the study, their rights to withdraw from the study at any time, and that the data that would be collected from them would be kept confidential. Consent was obtained from all participants prior to the start of the research study. Furthermore, the data that was collected was kept confidential, and any information that would identify the individuals that participated in the study was removed from the data after it was analyzed.

Results and Discussion

Extent of implementation of gender-responsive governance

Overall, the extent of the implementation of gender-responsive governance within the SAMARICA region is high (grand mean: 4.34; Table 1). In each of the four categories of gender-responsive governance, the mean scores for the region were high. Scores were highest for policies that aim to ensure the protection and promotion of the human rights of women (mean: 4.40). Following behind in score was local development plans and the GAD agenda, which received a mean score of 4.39. Mean scores of 4.37 indicate that policies concerning the establishment of institutional mechanisms within the region were established and implemented according to gender policy expectations. Finally, policies related to the allocation of resources to these institutions received a mean of 4.26; the lowest score among the four evaluated categories of gender policies, yet still indicative of a high standard of commitment to providing the necessary funds to support these initiatives. Thus, overall, gender-responsive governance policies are well-implemented within the region of SAMARICA.

In the SAMARICA area we see that gender responsive governance is very much the norm which in this case is in the women's human rights' protection and promotion. Also we have that Local Government Units are going beyond policy intent to show a great deal of commitment to gender equality through put in place structures and planning processes. Also there is a very consistent inclusion of the Gender and Development (GAD) agenda in local development plans which reports that gender issues are at the core of governance and not looked at as side issues.

This corroborates research indicating that robust institutional frameworks and right-based methodologies are essential for effective gender mainstreaming (Dar & Shaingorhri, 2022; Onamu et al, 2024). The research provides evidence that local governance can effectively implement gender-responsive policies when bolstered by political will and institutional capacity.

Factors	Overall Mean	Interpretation
Policies on the establishment of institutional mechanisms.	4.37	High
Policies on the protection and promotion of women's human rights.	4.40	High
Local development plans and GAD agenda	4.39	High
Resource allocation and financial accountability.	4.26	High
Grand Mean	4.34	High

Table 1. Summary of the extent of implementation of gender-responsive governance in SAMARICA area.

Quality of social service delivery in SAMARICA

The evaluation of the quality of social services provision in the SAMARICA region uniformly receives positive assessments. The mean of the various social service quality ratings is 4.29, with education receiving the highest rating of 4.35, followed by social welfare and development programs with a 4.32 mean, health services at 4.26, and safety and protection services with the lowest mean of 4.21. The findings indicate that the Local Government Units in the SAMARICA area provide good services to its citizens in various sectors. This suggests a strong commitment to meeting the social needs of their communities.

The study shows that LGU governance systems work well when they provide high-quality social services, especially in health, education, and social welfare. The robust performance across various sectors demonstrates that gender-responsive governance fosters inclusive and accessible services.

In line with previous studies, (David, 2018; Yapıcıoğlu & Aktepe, 2022), the finding confirm that community-focused, transparent, and adequately funded service delivery systems enhance public outcomes. The lower rating for safety and protection services, on the other hand, shows that this is an important area that needs to be improved, especially when it comes to protecting the vulnerable groups.

Factors	Overall Mean	Interpretation
Social welfare and development services.	4.32	Very good
Health service.	4.26	Very good
Safety and protection services.	4.21	Very good
Education-related services and facilities.	4.35	Very good
Grand Mean	4.29	Very good

Table 2. Summary of quality of social service delivery in SAMARICA area.

Level of community satisfaction with gender-responsive governance in SAMARICA area

The summary of the level of community satisfaction with gender-responsive governance in the SAMARICA area indicates that all assessed factors rated as high, with a grand mean of M=4.34. In all factors, policies on the protection and promotion of women's human rights received the highest rating (mean=4.32), followed closely by local development plans and the GAD agenda (mean=4.31), policies on the establishment of institutional mechanisms (mean=4.25), and resource allocation and financial accountability (mean=4.14). These results suggest that the community perceives the LGUs' efforts in promoting gender-responsive governance positively, particularly in terms of policy implementation and support for women's rights.

The community generally has a positive view of gender-responsive governance, but the results show that satisfaction is highest in areas that directly affect people's lives, like protecting women's rights. This suggests that the visibility and direct effects of policies are important factors in getting people to approve of them.

In line with previous research (Sijapati, 2023; Matahum & Tamique, 2025), the results demonstrate that community satisfaction enhances when governance initiatives are not only implemented but also perceived, acknowledged, and values by the public.

Factors	Overall Mean	Interpretation
Policies on the establishment of institutional mechanisms	4.25	High
Policies on the protection and promotion of women's human rights	4.32	High
Local development plans and GAD agenda	4.31	High
Resource allocation and financial accountability	4.14	High
Grand Mean	4.34	High

Table 3. Summary of the level of community satisfaction with gender-responsive governance in SAMARICA area.

Relationship between the extent of implementation of gender-responsive governance and the quality of social service delivery

Correlation analysis revealed that there is a strong and significant positive relationship between the extent of implementation of gender-responsive governance and the quality of social service delivery in the SAMARICA area ($r=.761$, $p=.001$). This suggest that the social service delivery is highly associated with the more effective and comprehensive implementation of all policies of gender responsive governance. Specifically, all components of gender-responsive governance showed significant correlations with various social service sectors.

For policies on the establishment of institutional mechanisms, correlations with social welfare and development services ($r=.583$, $p=.00$), health services ($r=.570$, $p=.00$), safety and protection services ($r=.505$, $p=.00$), and education-related services ($r=.594$, $p=.00$) were all significant and at moderate levels. Policies on the protection and promotion of women's human rights exhibited even stronger relationships, particularly with social welfare and development services ($r=.661$, $p=.00$) and health services ($r=.577$, $p=.00$), while correlations with safety and protection ($r=.561$, $p=.00$) and education services ($r=.506$, $p=.00$) were also significant. Although numerically higher, the correlation is still at moderate level.

Similarly, the integration of gender-responsive governance in local development plans and GAD agendas was significantly associated with social welfare and development ($r=.621$, $p=.00$), health ($r=.589$, $p=.00$), safety and protection ($r=.476$, $p=.00$), and education services ($r=.604$, $p=.00$). Resource allocation and financial accountability also showed significant positive correlations across all service areas, with coefficients ranging from $r=.529$ for safety and protection services to $r=.603$ for social welfare and development services, all at $p=.00$.

The strong connection between gender-responsive governance and better service delivery suggests that gender mainstreaming improves the effectiveness and inclusivity of public services.

Institutional structures, gender sensitive planning, and proper resource allocation together which in turn improve service outcomes. We find out that includes gender issues in governance structures improves the response and equity of service delivery which we also report to be true in the work of Sagcal and Ramos (2024). Also it is put forth that gender responsive governance is a tool in which we see to produce better development results.

Implementation of Gender-Responsive Governance	Quality of Social Service Delivery	r	p-value	Description
Policies on the establishment of institutional mechanisms	Social welfare and development services	.583***	.00	Significant
	Health service	.570***	.00	Significant
	Safety and protection services	.505***	.00	Significant
	Education-related services and facilities	.594***	.00	Significant
Policies on the protection and promotion of women's human rights	Social welfare and development services	.661***	.00	Significant
	Health service	.577***	.00	Significant
	Safety and protection services	.561***	.00	Significant
Local development plans and GAD agenda	Education-related services and facilities	.506***	.00	Significant
	Social welfare and development services	.621***	.00	Significant
	Health service	.589***	.00	Significant
	Safety and protection services	.476***	.00	Significant

Resource allocation and financial accountability	Education-related services and facilities	.604***	.00	Significant
	Social welfare and development services	.603***	.00	Significant
	Health service	.596***	.00	Significant
	Safety and protection services	.529***	.00	Significant
	Education-related services and facilities	.573***	.00	Significant
Overall		.761***	.00	Significant

Table 4. Relationship between the extent of implementation of gender-responsive governance and the quality of social service delivery in SAMARICA area.

Relationship between the extent of implementation and the level of community satisfaction with gender-responsive governance in SAMARICA area

The results indicate that there is no significant relationship between the extent of implementation of gender-responsive governance and the level of community satisfaction with these governance practices in the SAMARICA area [Table 5]. Across the different components of implementation, including policies on the establishment of institutional mechanisms, protection and promotion of women's human rights, integration in local development plans and GAD agendas, and resource allocation and financial accountability, correlation coefficients with community satisfaction were very low, ranging from $r=0.003$ to $r=0.137$, and none were statistically significant at the 0.05 level, except for a single weak correlation between policies on the protection and promotion of women's human rights and the corresponding satisfaction indicator ($r=0.137$, $p=0.012$), which, despite its statistical significance, is too low to indicate a meaningful relationship.

The overall correlation ($r = 0.052$, $p = 0.34$) indicates that higher levels of gender-responsive governance implementation do not necessarily correspond to higher community satisfaction. This suggests that while policies may be formally implemented, other factors such as awareness, accessibility, or perceived effectiveness of services, may influence community satisfaction independently of the degree of policy implementation.

This study would like to target is that a policy's implementation doesn't always guarantee community support. The findings of this research study illustrate the difference between the implementation of policies as compared to the perception of such policies by the public. Many empirical studies show that the public's reaction and participation in the policies created by the government is influenced by various factors (Hafez et al., 2022; Anderson et al., 2021). These findings indicate that the implementation of policies is not always accompanied by positive public sentiment towards those policies. Thus, the findings contribute to the discussion of the importance of including the public in the creation and implementation of policies.

Implementation of Gender-Responsive Governance	Community Satisfaction with Gender-Responsive Governance	r	p-value	Description
Policies on the establishment of institutional mechanisms	Policies on the establishment of institutional mechanisms	0.065	0.231	Not significant
	Policies on the protection and promotion of women's human rights	0.049	0.37	Not significant
	Local development plans and GAD agenda	0.042	0.443	Not significant
	Resource allocation and financial accountability	0.073	0.184	Not significant
Policies on the protection and promotion of women's human rights	Policies on the establishment of institutional mechanisms	0.077	0.158	Not significant

	Policies on the protection and promotion of women's human rights	0.137*	0.012	Not significant
	Local development plans and GAD agenda	0.093	0.088	Not significant
	Resource allocation and financial accountability	0.106	0.053	Not significant
	Policies on the establishment of institutional mechanisms	0.01	0.862	Not significant
Local development plans and GAD agenda	Policies on the protection and promotion of women's human rights	0.034	0.533	Not significant
	Local development plans and GAD agenda	0.003	0.959	Not significant
	Resource allocation and financial accountability	0.004	0.941	Not significant
	Policies on the establishment of institutional mechanisms	0.003	0.954	Not significant
Resource allocation and financial accountability	Policies on the protection and promotion of women's human rights	0.006	0.919	Not significant
	Local development plans and GAD agenda	0.025	0.642	Not significant
	Resource allocation and financial accountability	0.003	0.961	Not significant
	Overall	0.052	0.34	Not significant

Table 5. Relationship between the extent of implementation and the level of community satisfaction with gender-responsive governance in SAMARICA area.

Relationship between the quality of social service delivery and the level of community satisfaction with gender-responsive governance

As revealed in Table 6, overall, there is no significant relationship between the quality of social service delivery and the level of community satisfaction with gender-responsive governance in the SAMARICA area, with an overall correlation of $r=0.062$, $p=0.259$. This suggests that higher quality of social services does not automatically translate to higher community satisfaction with gender-responsive governance.

When examined by service sector, most correlations between social welfare and development services, health services, and education-related services with the different components of gender-responsive governance, such as policies on institutional mechanisms, protection and promotion of women's human rights, local development plans and GAD agenda, and resource allocation, were very low and not statistically significant (ranging from $r=0.013$ to $r=0.082$, $p>0.05$).

The only exclusion were observed in safety and protection services, where weak but significant positive correlations were found with policies on the establishment of institutional mechanisms ($r=0.109$, $p=0.046$) and with policies on the protection and promotion of women's human rights ($r=0.114$, $p=0.036$). These findings imply that while improvements in safety and protection services can have some impact on community satisfaction with certain gender-responsive governance policies, the effect appears to be relatively small. The results highlight that other factors beyond service quality likely shape community perceptions and satisfaction with gender-responsive governance.

The lack of a clear connection between most service delivery areas and community satisfaction shows that improving service quality alone will not be enough to change views on gender-responsive governance. Only safety and protection services provide a significant impact.

This finding corroborates Lian et al. (2022), who contend that satisfaction is contingent not only upon service quality but also on trust, communication, and perceived relevance. The argument emphasizes that that good governance requires both practical effectiveness and the quality of relationships within the community.

Implementation of Gender-Responsive Governance	Community Satisfaction with Gender-Responsive Governance	r	p-value	Description
Social welfare and development services	Policies on the establishment of institutional mechanisms	0.02	0.718	Not significant
	Policies on the protection and promotion of women's human rights	0.082	0.133	Not significant
	Local development plans and GAD agenda	0.044	0.417	Not significant
	Resource allocation and financial accountability	0.032	0.554	Not significant
	Policies on the establishment of institutional mechanisms	0.054	0.321	Not significant
Health service	Policies on the protection and promotion of women's human rights	0.054	0.327	Not significant
	Local development plans and GAD agenda	0.03	0.588	Not significant
	Resource allocation and financial accountability	0.066	0.229	Not significant
	Policies on the establishment of institutional mechanisms	.109*	0.046	Significant
Safety and protection services	Policies on the protection and promotion of women's human rights	.114*	0.036	Significant
	Local development plans and GAD agenda	0.081	0.138	Not significant
	Resource allocation and financial accountability	0.075	0.169	Not significant
	Policies on the establishment of institutional mechanisms	0.014	0.795	Not significant
Education-related services and facilities	Policies on the protection and promotion of women's human rights	0.018	0.742	Not significant
	Local development plans and GAD agenda	0.04	0.461	Not significant
	Resource allocation and financial accountability	0.013	0.812	Not significant
	Overall	0.062	0.259	Not significant

Table 6. Relationship between the quality of social service delivery and the level of community satisfaction with gender-responsive governance in SAMARICA area.

Indicators of implementation of gender-responsive governance that best predict the community satisfaction in SAMARICA area

Table 7 shows that among the indicators of gender-responsive governance, only policies on the protection and promotion of women's human rights significantly predict community satisfaction in the SAMARICA area ($\beta=0.198$, $t=2.556$, $p=0.01$). This convey that when these policies are effectively implemented, they have a measurable positive impact on how the community perceives and responds to gender-responsive governance. Other indicators, including policies on the establishment of institutional mechanisms ($\beta=0.085$, $t=1.030$, $p=0.304$), local development plans and GAD agenda ($\beta=0.107$,

t=1.190, p=0.235), and resource allocation and financial accountability ($\beta=0.105$, t=1.321, p=0.187), were not significant predictors of community satisfaction.

The model explains only a small portion of the variance in community satisfaction, as indicated by the low Multiple R-squared=0.028 and Adjusted R-squared=0.016, with the overall model approaching but not reaching conventional significance (F=2.360, p=0.053). This indicates that while protection and promotion of women's human rights is a key predictor, other unmeasured factors likely influence community satisfaction with gender-responsive governance in the area.

Safety and protection services appear to be the most important factor when it comes to services. The results highlighted the importance of communities prioritizing the deliverables that directly influence their idea of security and dignity. This offers actionable direction for policymakers, facilitating in which area to focus with the greatest potential impact when improving gender-responsive initiatives.

Independent Variable	β	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Policies on the establishment of institutional mechanisms	.085	1.030	.304	Not significant
Policies on the protection and promotion of women's human rights	.198	2.556	.011	Significant
Local development plans and GAD agenda	.107	1.190	.235	Not significant
Resource allocation and financial accountability	.105	1.321	.187	Not significant

Table 7. Indicators of implementation of gender-responsive governance that best predict the community satisfaction in SAMARICA area.

Indicators of quality of social service delivery that best predict the community satisfaction with gender-responsive governance in SAMARICA area

As presented in Table 8, among the indicators of the quality of social service delivery, only safety and protection services significantly predict community satisfaction with gender-responsive governance in the SAMARICA area ($\beta=0.177$, t=2.091, p=0.037). This suggests that improvements in safety and protection services are associated with higher levels of community satisfaction, highlighting the importance of these services in shaping public perceptions of gender-responsive governance. Other service indicators, including social welfare and development services ($\beta=0.026$, t=0.328, p=0.743), health services ($\beta=0.029$, t=0.319, p=0.750), and education-related services and facilities ($\beta=0.163$, t=1.910, p=0.057), were not significant predictors of community satisfaction.

The overall model explains a small portion of the variance in community satisfaction, as reflected by the low Multiple R-squared=0.023 and Adjusted R-squared=0.011, with the model not reaching conventional significance (F=1.921, p=0.106). This indicates that while safety and protection services are important, other factors beyond the measured quality of social services likely influence community satisfaction with gender-responsive governance in the area.

Independent Variable	β	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Social welfare and development services	.026	.328	.743	Not significant
Health service	.029	.319	.750	Not significant
Safety and protection services	.177	2.091	.037	Significant
Education-related services and facilities	.163	1.910	.057	Not significant

Table 8. Indicators of quality of social service delivery that best predict the community satisfaction with gender-responsive governance in SAMARICA area.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The research indicates that gender-responsive governance within the SAMARICA area is highly effective. Significant collective efforts from various local government offices are being made to protect women's rights, integrate the Gender and Development (GAD) agenda into local development plans, and strengthen institutional frameworks that support gender equality.

Furthermore, community members show a positive assessment of social service quality, assigning high ratings to educational, social welfare, and healthcare provisions.

The findings suggest that local government bodies within the SAMARICA area are noticeably committed to promoting gender-responsive governance, concurrently providing crucial public services designed to meet community standards and requirements. However, research indicates that the implementation of gender-responsive policies or the expansion of social services does not necessarily correlate with increased community satisfaction.

Only governance efforts that are specifically designed to protect women's rights and provide safety and protection services have a clear effect on how people feel about governance. This finding shows how much communities participate about programs that have to do with their rights, safety, and general well-being. Therefore, local governments should make protective programs a top priority in their governance frameworks.

Acknowledgement

The researcher would like to express her sincerest gratitude and heartfelt appreciation to the individuals whose guidance, expertise, and support greatly contributed to the successful completion of this Master's thesis in Public Administration.

Funding

This research received no external funding from any public, commercial, or not-for-profit funding agency, and no organization provided financial support for the conduct of the study, authorship, or publication of this article.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

References

- Anderson, D., Gupta, A., Birken, S., Sakas, Z., & Freeman, M. (2021). Successes, challenges, and support for men versus women implementers in water, sanitation, and hygiene programs: A qualitative study in rural Nepal. *International journal of hygiene and environmental health*, 236, 113792. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2021.113792>.
- Audette, A., Lam, S., O'Connor, H., & Radcliff, B. (2018). (E)Quality of Life: A Cross-National Analysis of the Effect of Gender Equality on Life Satisfaction. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10902-018-0042-8>.
- Dar, S., & Shairgojri, A. (2022). Role of Women in Good Governance. *Journal of Social Science*. <https://doi.org/10.46799/jss.v3i4.360>.
- David, O., & T, B. (2018). Social Service Delivery in Southwestern Nigeria: Local Governments Perspective. *Journal of Public Administration and Governance*, 8, 294-310. <https://doi.org/10.5296/jpag.v8i4.14131>.
- Denhart, J. & Denhart, R. (2015). The New Public Service. *Serving, Not Steering*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315709765>
- Hafez, S., Munyi, B., Zeno, K., Gbozee, C., Jusu, M., Reeves, M., Wesseh, C., Wiah, S., Alkhalidi, M., Johnson, K., & Subah, M. (2022). Examining the gender imbalance in the National Community Health Assistant Programme in Liberia: a qualitative analysis of policy and Programme implementation. *Health Policy and Planning*, 38, 181 - 191. <https://doi.org/10.1093/heapol/czac075>.
- Lian, X., Li, D., Di, W., Oubibi, M., Zhang, X., Zhang, S., Xu, C., & Lu, H. (2022). Research on Influential Factors of Satisfaction for Residents in Unit Communities—Taking Ningbo City as an Example. DOI:10.3390/su14116687
- Matahum, A., & Tanigue, Y. (2025). The Extent of Implementation of The Local Government Unit of RA 9262 in Eliminating Violence Against Women and Children in the National Capital Region. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*. <https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.06.04.24>.
- National Commission on the Role of Filipino Women and the Department of the Interior and Local Government- Local Government Academy (NCRFW and DILG LGA). (2005). Gender Responsive LGU (GeRL) Ka Ba? Self-Assessment Instrument. Manila: NCRFW and DILG-LGA.
- Onamu, B., Matanga, F., & Odhiambo, E. (2024). The Nature of Gender Mainstreaming Policies in Nakuru and Narok Counties, Kenya. *African Journal of Empirical Research*. <https://doi.org/10.51867/ajernet.5.4.104>.
- Philippine Commission on Women (2018). Gender-Responsive LGU assessment tool https://calabarzon.neda.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/GeRL-Assessment-Tool_PCW_03142019.pdf

- Republic Act No. 9710 (2008). Magna Carta Of Women.
<https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/downloads/2009/08aug/20090814-RA-9710-GMA.pdf>
- Sagcal, M., & Ramos, V. (2024). An Evaluation On The Institutionalization Of Gender And Development (GAD) Program In Selected Barangays In Lupao, Nueva Ecija. *The QUEST: Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*.
<https://doi.org/10.60008/thequest.v3i1.176>.
- Sijapati, D. (2023). The Allocation of Gender-Responsive Budget with Local Governance in Nepal. *Advances in Sciences and Humanities*. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ash.20230901.11>.
- UNDP, (2021). UNDP Annual Report 2021. <https://www.undp.org/publications/undp-annual-report-2021>.
- Yapicioglu, E., & Aktepe, E. (2022). Local Service Delivery Problem: Social Services. *Cankiri Karatekin Universitesi Iktisadi ve Idari Bilimler Fakultesi Dergisi*. <https://doi.org/10.18074/ckuiibfd.1128950>.

Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.